

Development of an *in vitro* pig gut model for evaluating factors driving antimicrobial resistance

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Aim: The study aimed to further develop an *in vitro* continuous flow model representing the large intestine of the pig. The model was employed to determine the factors driving the transfer of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) through transformation and conjugation events.

Methods: A continuous flow *in vitro* pig gut model composed of six independent vessels under anaerobic controlled conditions was set up. The model was seeded with pooled pig faecal slurry to simulate the intestinal microflora. To study AMR transfer, the model was inoculated with a sodium azide resistant *E. coli* J53 strain, while amplicons of the RNA polymerase β subunit (*rpoB*) gene conferring resistance to rifampicin used as a source of extracellular DNA.

Results: The *in vitro* gut model was set up and validated with conditions such as temperature, pH and flow rate optimised for the pig. Rifampicin resistant mutants were generated in *E. coli* J53, and the lack of intrinsic fitness burden was confirmed. Preliminary natural transformation using *E. coli* J53 as the recipient strain (rifampicin sensitive) and the *rpoB* DNA amplicon as the donor DNA (rifampicin resistant) demonstrated successful recovery of transformants of *E. coli* J53 that were both sodium azide and rifampicin resistant.

Conclusions: An *in vitro* pig gut model was developed and validated to determine the role of trace elements, heavy metals and/or antibiotics in the acquisition of AMR-encoding extracellular DNA. The study concluded that the transformation of extracellular DNA into *E. coli* J53 successfully increased AMR, and driving factors will be further investigated. The findings from this study maybe helpful in the development of mitigation strategies.

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